

WebChuck: Computer Music Programming on the Web

Michael R. Mulshine
CCRMA, Stanford University
Stanford, CA, United States
mulshine@ccrma.stanford.edu

Ge Wang
CCRMA, Stanford University
Stanford, CA, United States
ge@ccrma.stanford.edu

Jack Atherton
CCRMA, Stanford University
Stanford, CA, United States
lja@ccrma.stanford.edu

Chris Chafe
CCRMA, Stanford University
Stanford, CA, United States
cc@ccrma.stanford.edu

Terry Feng
CCRMA, Stanford University
Stanford, CA, United States
tzfeng@ccrma.stanford.edu

Celeste Betancur
CCRMA, Stanford University
Stanford, CA, United States
celes@ccrma.stanford.edu

Figure 1: From left to right: WebChuck IDE, A browser-based "wind machine," controlling ChuckK from Javascript code, web-hosted virtual instruments written in ChuckK.

ABSTRACT

WebChuck is ChuckK—a *strongly-timed* computer music programming language—running on the web. Recent advancements in browser technology (including WebAssembly and the Web Audio API's `AudioWorklet` interface) have enabled languages written in C/C++ (like ChuckK) to run in web browsers with nearly native-code performance. Early adopters have explored the many practical and creative possibilities that WebChuck enables, ranging from a WebChuck integrated development environment to interactive browser-based audiovisual experiences. WebChuck has also been adopted as the programming platform in an introductory computer music course at Stanford University. Importantly, by running in any browser, WebChuck broadens and simplifies access to computer music programming, opening the door for new users and creative workflows. In this paper, we discuss WebChuck and its applications to date, explain how the tool was designed and implemented, and evaluate the unique affordances of combining computer music programming with a web development workflow.

WebChuck portal:
<https://chuck.stanford.edu/webchuck/>

Author Keywords

WebChuck, ChuckK, audio programming, web programming, web audio, browser IDE, accessibility

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → **Sound and music computing**; • **Information systems** → *Web interfaces*; • **Human-centered computing** → *Systems and tools for interaction design*;

1. WHAT IS WEBCHUCK?

Computer music programming languages began on main-frame computers and evolved their way into desktops, laptops, mobile phones, and more. But until recently, fully-programmable audio synthesis on the web was not feasible, primarily due to limitations of the web platform. Browsers have not been powerful enough to tackle high CPU-load tasks like digital signal processing and other low-level audio code (often written in C/C++, which browsers don't natively support). On top of this, lack of cross-compatibility between browsers has limited the scope and potential impact of web-based audio development.

Fortunately, advancements and widespread adoption of key features of the Web Audio API[10] (such as the `AudioWorklet`¹ interface) and other tools (like `emscripten`², which enable C/C++ libraries to be compiled into We-

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). Copyright remains with the author(s).

NIME'23, 31 May–2 June, 2023, Mexico City, Mexico.

¹<https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/API/AudioWorklet>

²<https://emscripten.org/>

bAssembly³ binaries) have opened a pathway for computer music languages written in C and C++ to run on the web.[8][9][7] Additionally, some intrepid exploration of what it means to do audio programming on the web has led to the creation of a slew of tools and web experiences.

With WebChuck, we merge the low-level control capabilities and expressiveness of the computer music programming language ChuckK with the ease, accessibility, interactivity, portability, and ubiquity offered by the web. Specifically, this introduces several advantages:

1. WebChuck brings a fully-featured computer music programming to the web, and along with it capabilities such as unit generators, unit analyzers, audio DSP, music interaction design tools
2. It combines the sample-synchronous, *strongly-timed*, and concurrent features of the ChuckK language with the workflow and trappings (web pages, web GUIs, high performance graphics, collaboration) of the web
3. Like other web-based programming tools, it broadens the reach and accessibility of audio and highly-synchronized audiovisual programming for educators, artists, and audiences around the world

This paper will be most useful for users of ChuckK, but also highlights (via use-case examples) some of the key affordances that audio programming on the web, in general, may bring to the community. To learn more about ChuckK, get started on the ChuckK website.⁴

1.1 A Brief History of WebChuck

The ChuckK programming language [17] was initially released in 2003 [16], marking this year as the 20th anniversary of ChuckK. Over this period, ChuckK has been used in sound synthesis, instrument design, laptop orchestras, mobile music apps, audiovisual and VR design, generative music systems, and many more artistic, educational, and research contexts. The defining features of ChuckK are:

- A sample-precise unified timing mechanism for multi-rate event and control processing. This *strongly-timed* property of the language effectively removes the distinction between audio and control rate traditionally found in languages such as CSound, Max/MSP, and SuperCollider.
- A simple but powerful concurrent programming model based on time—allowing for audio programs to be expressed precisely and in parallel.
- A live coding environment (and way of thinking) that supports rapid experimentation, teaching/learning, and performance.

ChuckK was designed with the idea that the form of a tool shapes the way we think [15]. ChuckK exists in various forms including command-line `chuck`, `miniAudicle` (a graphical IDE; [13]), `ChiP` (ChuckK on the iPhone; [14]), `FauCK` (ChuckK in FAUST; [18]), `Chunity` (ChuckK in Unity; [5]), and more recently, `ChAI` (ChuckK for AI, in early development) and `WebChuck`. The development of the latter resulted from a collective effort:

- After a number of attempts by the ChuckK community to compile the C++ code base from ChuckK to WebAssembly using `emscripten`, Jack Atherton, then a

Ph.D. candidate in Ge Wang’s Music, Computing, Design research group, achieved this in 2020 and devised the core functionality of `WebChuck`.

- Soon after, Mike Mulshine began creating web-based audiovisual art, tutorials, and demos⁵ using `WebChuck` and `p5.js`, and organized ambassadorial efforts to bring `WebChuck` to new audiences.
- In 2022, Chris Chafe transitioned from using `ChuckK` to `WebChuck` as a teaching tool at Stanford University’s popular Music 220a course “The Foundations of Computer-Generated Sound.”⁶
- Terry Feng and Celeste Betancur developed the `WebChuck` IDE in 2022, and designed tools for real-time visualization and code-based GUI-generation for the IDE.

1.2 Using WebChuck

There are two general approaches to using `WebChuck`:

1. As a **web-based programming tool** for sound design, interaction design, composition, and teaching
2. As a **component** in larger web-based artworks, tools, and games.

Figure 2: The `WebChuck` IDE running some 808 kick synthesis.

Using `ChuckK` as a **web-based programming tool** entails simply navigating to the dedicated `WebChuck` IDE⁷, pictured in Figure 2), and writing `ChuckK` code. The IDE provides the ability to perform typical `ChuckK`-environment actions like starting the virtual machine, adding and removing `ChuckK` shreds, and printing to the `ChuckK` console. This form factor is friendly to students, creative prototypers, and anyone wishing to “jump in” and start coding without installing any software. An activity monitor displays all currently running shreds and enables users to selectively add or remove them from the virtual machine. Audio and other data files can be loaded into `WebChuck` for use from code.

The second approach, using `WebChuck` as a **component** within a larger web-based project, involves embedding the `ChuckK` `WebAssembly` (`wasm`) module and `JavaScript` interface. The latter provides a suite of “getter” and “setter” methods to modify or retrieve global variables in `ChuckK` from a browser script, enabling a two-way workflow in which web page elements can both control or be controlled by

⁵<https://mikemulshine.com/webchuck-demo/>

⁶<https://ccrma.stanford.edu/courses/220a/>

⁷<https://chuck.stanford.edu/webchuck/>

³<https://webassembly.org/>

⁴<https://chuck.stanford.edu/>

ChucK code. For example, it is possible to control audio synthesis parameters using GUI elements, mouse movement, keyboard input, and MIDI controllers. Working in tandem with JavaScript libraries (like *p5.js* or *Three.js*) and other web UI development platforms, WebChucK supports a tightly-synchronized audiovisual workflow for web-based art and other creative applications. Lastly, it is important to note that WebChucK runs entirely on the client-side browser, requiring no backend server-side support other than a static HTML web page.

1.3 Example Use Cases

To give a sense of WebChucK in action, here are some example use cases:

1. **Quick prototyping:** anyone with a supported browser can navigate to the online IDE
2. **Sharing:** Upon being asked to produce some wind sound for the Stanford Symphony Orchestra's performance of Richard Strauss's *Don Quixote*, Chris prototyped a generative wind machine with a scrolling interactive spectrogram with WebChucK and basic HTML/JavaScript. He simply sent the link to the Orchestra.⁸ For context, compare these two methods:
 - **Existing method of sharing ChucK code:**
 - "Here is a ChucK file..."
 - "Go to this URL, download and install ChucK..."
 - "Open miniAudicle, start Virtual Machine, open the file, hit 'plus' (or run it in a terminal emulator)..."
 - "If it doesn't work, let us know!"⁹
 - **New method of sharing with WebChucK:**
 - "Here's a URL."
3. **Creating virtual instruments:** Connect a MIDI keyboard, and start playing immediately. Jack's Timbre Library¹⁰ for ChucK (hosted on the web) provides several examples of web-based virtual synths in action.
4. **Teaching:** Students can start coding audio right away. WebChucK removes much of the technical overhead of operating systems, software installation, terminals, GUIs, and audio interfaces.
5. **Doing computer music in new ways:** In our experience, WebChucK isn't just a more portable version of ChucK, but affords some new functionalities and ways of working that didn't exist or weren't feasible before. We describe some examples of this in Section 4.

To learn more about how to embed WebChucK in your own web project, work through a few simple tutorials here: <https://chuck.stanford.edu/webchuck/tutorial/>

2. RELATED WORK

Three primary approaches to programming with audio on the web exist. The first approach involves embedding audio on a web page via the HTML `<audio>` element. This enables simple playback of audio files, triggered by user interaction

⁸<https://ccrma.stanford.edu/~cc/windMachine/>

⁹One could imagine a similar workflow for languages like Max/MSP or SuperCollider.

¹⁰Timbre Library link: <https://ccrma.stanford.edu/~lja/timbre-library/>

with UI elements like buttons or `autoplay`. Dynamic real-time control of this audio is limited.

The second approach is to use and extend the Web Audio API. The *p5.js* library has implemented their own JavaScript wrapper around Web Audio called `p5.sound`¹¹, which provides a set of easy-to-use audio playback, synthesis, and analysis functions to web developers, like `p5.SoundFile`, `p5.Oscillator`, `p5.Envelope`, and more. *Three.js* provides an analogous tool in their `Audio` object, which primarily provides functions to manipulate the playback of audio files. Similarly, *Tone.js*¹² extends the Web Audio API and offers handy methods (e.g. via `Tone.Transport`) for dealing with musical timing in JavaScript.

More advanced and musically-tailored web-based audio platforms and live-coding languages have been developed by extending the Web Audio API, including Tidal Cycles¹³ (a live-coding tool for music generation developed in Haskell and compiled into JavaScript[12]), Gibber¹⁴ (a live audio programming language with a great depth of sound and music generation capabilities and unique text-animated graphical UI), CodeCircle[20] (shown to be a useful tool in prototyping instruments on the web), Estuary[3] (a live-coding platform that enables the simultaneous use of many live coding languages at once, as an "ensemble"), and Strudel[4] (an alternative to Tidal Cycles with an algorithmic composition focus). These useful and expressive tools each offer unique affordances for programming audio in a web-based IDE, live coding and performance, and audio development projects. Built in JavaScript around the Web Audio API, they make audio control more accessible for web developers and artists, despite lacking some of the low-level audio programming control (e.g. sample-by-sample synthesis) and flexibility of a full-fledged computer music programming languages like ChucK, Super Collider, Csound, and others.

The third approach involves porting an entire computer music language to the web using tools (e.g. `emscripten`) to create a WebAssembly binary and run it via Web Audio's `AudioWorklet` interface[6]. ChucK is not the only computer music programming language that now runs in this manner in the browser. Others include the functional audio signal processing language FAUST[1], with their custom IDE[2] tailored for compiling and exporting FAUST code as audio programs ready for use in a variety of other environments (from iOS apps to firmware on microcontrollers like Teensy). The Csound IDE[19]¹⁵ brings Barry Vercoe's Csound to the web as a user-friendly social audio programming environment. The graph-oriented live coding language (nicknamed Glicol¹⁶) compiles desktop Glicol into WebAssembly running via the `AudioWorklet` interface and provides a sleek and modern IDE. Additionally, there have been community efforts bring SuperCollider and Pure Data¹⁷ to the web. The developers of ChucK are excited to join the fold in bringing audio programming languages to the web.

3. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

At its core, WebChucK is ChucK running as a `WebAssembly` binary in a `AudioWorkletNode`¹⁸, inheriting the ben-

¹¹<https://p5js.org/reference/#/libraries/p5.sound>

¹²<https://tonejs.github.io/>

¹³<https://tidalcycles.org/>

¹⁴<https://gibber.cc/>

¹⁵<https://ide.csound.com/>

¹⁶<https://glicol.org/>

¹⁷<https://github.com/sebpiq/WebPd>

¹⁸<https://developer.chrome.com/blog/audio-worklet-design-pattern/>

efits of WebAssembly’s high-performance virtual machine as well as its managed container and fine-grained security model. Compiled directly from the ChuckK source (C/C++) using `emscripten`, `webchuck.wasm` contains ChuckK’s compiler, virtual machine, class libraries, unit generators, and unit analyzers.

Next, an accompanying `webchuck.js` component provides JavaScript bindings to approximately 50 entry points into the C++ ChuckK runtime as embedded in the `Wasm` module. It also handles messages passed through the port message interface between the browser thread and an `AudioWorkletNode`. `webchuck.js` also defines the `ChuckNode` and `ChuckSubNode` classes, each of which extends Web Audio’s `AudioWorkletProcessor` and manages the ChuckK core from within the `AudioWorklet` thread.

A WebChuck host (`webchuck_host.js`) provides helper functions for starting the Web Audio environment, initializing a ChuckK instance within that environment as well as messaging mechanisms. The host associates `webchuck.js`’s `ChuckNode` to an `AudioWorkletNode` that can be modularly connected to the audio routing graph in the browser’s audio context (`AudioContext`). In general, this host serves as a API for the ChuckK runtime.

`webchuck.wasm`, `webchuck.js`, and some form of `webchuck_host.js` exist in all WebChuck projects; the latest released version is made accessible online¹⁹. Embedding these components makes it straightforward to do the following in a web development context:

1. **Write normal ChuckK code**, passed as strings or files to the ChuckK runtime. This enables the dynamic addition of ChuckK shreds during the lifetime of the web page. Each shred has an ID enabling the removal or replacement of shreds with some simple data management.
2. **Communicate between ChuckK and JavaScript**. Running ChuckK on the browser can be useful as a self-contained audio engine, but further control and flexibility is possible via a collection of “getter” and “setter” methods that allow developers to modify variables or trigger events between ChuckK and web-based elements in real-time. This two-way communication enables the creation of web pages with synchronized and controllable audio and UI events (e.g., a slider on a web page can directly control a synthesis parameter in ChuckK; meanwhile, precisely timed events in ChuckK can drive web-based graphics and visualization).
3. **Take advantage of familiar workflows**. Audio, MIDI, and other data files can be loaded into the ChuckK node for playback, sonification, or other creative uses. The WebChuckK JavaScript API provides a few simple methods for file data to be accessed from within ChuckK. Furthermore, a `chuckPrint()` method pipes anything printed in ChuckK code to the browser console, for debugging and general output.

Preparing the ChuckK code base for compilation to WebChuckK involved some reworking of the source. While the vast majority of ChuckK functionality is present in WebChuckK, at the time of this writing the following native ChuckK functionalities are selectively disabled:

- HID devices (keyboard, mouse, joystick)
- serial communication

- network communication (including Open Sound Control)
- OTF server (used to receive commands like “shred” over the network)
- ChuckK watchdog (detects possible time-less infinite loops)
- ChuckK shell (interactive prompt mode)

While these functionalities are currently not supported in WebChuckK itself, several of these (HID, serial, network communication, OSC) can be implemented in JavaScript and communicated to ChuckK.

4. APPLICATIONS AND EVALUATION

We feel that an evaluation of a tool like WebChuckK is most meaningfully carried out by an examination of what people have been able to build and do with it, considering both the unique affordances and limitations encountered as result of using the tool.

Many students and several artists have begun to explore and demonstrate the varied uses of WebChuckK. Chris Chafe taught CCRMA’s popular “Introduction to Computer-Generated Sound” course entirely with WebChuckK in the fall quarter of 2022. Student projects ranged from compositional exercises in data sonification to full-fledged browser-based instruments. Some notable student projects (pictured in Figure 3) include:

1. **Chauvet Cave Beep Ploc Symphony**²⁰, by Luna Valentin: A data sonification project examining the effect of increased extreme weather phenomena on the ecological balance of caves in France, previously inhabited by our Paleolithic ancestors 36,000 years ago.
2. **Image Sonifier**²¹, by Cole Simmons: An image-to-sound converter that uploads an image from the user, retrieves various parameters like minimum and maximum hue and saturation, and sonifies the calculated data with ChuckK.
3. **Barrel Synth: A Feedback-Based Browser Instrument**²², by Josh Mitchell: A unique virtual instrument taking influence from Tom Mudd’s Gutter Synthesis algorithm[11]. A bank of sliders allows you to control the gain (and, therefore, feedback) between a set of chaotic duffing oscillators and modal resonators routed to and from one another.

Figure 3: Left to right: Chauvet Cave Beep Ploc, Image Sonifier, Barrel Synth: A Feedback-Based Browser Instrument.

²⁰<https://ccrma.stanford.edu/~luna/220a/fp>

²¹<https://image-sonification.vercel.app/>

²²<https://ccrma.stanford.edu/~jomitch/220a/fp>

¹⁹<https://chuck.stanford.edu/webchuck/src/>

These projects all combined real-time audio generation in ChuckK with web-based UI elements like buttons, sliders, graphs, images, and more, and can run in browser environments across platforms. Typically, ChuckK developers need to go through a substantial process to incorporate ChuckK natively in audiovisual environments such as Unity, or set up an Open Sound Control pipeline between ChuckK code and graphics generated in another program (C++, Processing, OpenFrameworks etc.). Instead, WebChuckK places ChuckK squarely in the world of WebAssembly and web UI/UX, immediately making WebChuckK programs compatible across operating systems. This allows ChuckK to be extended in web plugins, extensions, modules, web games, or audiovisual creations, as the course projects above demonstrate. Reflecting on his own experiences in the same course, co-author Terry Feng²³ notes that WebChuckK is a “one size fits all” tool, specifically in the way it unifies audio and visual development workflows into one environment to serve a user base across many platforms.

Celeste Betancur²⁴, an avid ChuckK programmer and live-coding performing artist, suggested that one of the core advantages of using ChuckK on the web is in the powerful timing and scheduling workflow it enables. By contrast, using JavaScript alone, the timing of events is achieved via functions like `setTimeout()` and `setInterval()`, which delay or perform the execution of a script at specific time intervals. Similarly, the Web Audio API provides timing mechanisms that specify when a node starts or stops its processing via the parent class `AudioScheduledSourceNode`’s `start([time])` and `stop([time])` functions, or schedule parameter automation via `AudioParam`’s `setValueAtTime()`, `linearRampToValueAtTime()`, and other functions. These methods require a rather clunky mode of development and no granular control over timing and scheduling. ChuckK, on the other hand, provides sample-accurate control of how time progresses on any number of threads (“shreds”). This allows powerful schedulers and the ability to communicate Events and variables to the browser-based UI (e.g., musical events in ChuckK triggering graphical events on the web page).

Celeste also reflects that WebChuckK is a helpful tool for prototyping live computer-music performance. One can quickly trial creative ideas with ChuckK code in the browser without having to manage a desktop development workflow (e.g., command line, audio settings, file systems etc.).

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 What have we learned so far?

WebChuckK is a viable (and often fun) way to ChuckK. There are some limitations that come with the medium of web browsers (e.g., network security, which so far has precluded native networking features). At the same time, WebChuckK has added to the ecosystem in terms of what one can do with ChuckK and expanded *who* can work—and has access to—the medium of programmable sound and music. WebChuckK lets users code with ChuckK on their favorite modern browsers, both on desktop platforms (macOS, Windows, Linux) and on mobile phones (iOS and Android). It leverages the sonic and musical affordances of ChuckK with the many features of the web, making possible new and more accessible modes of audiovisual application development.

As discussed in Section 2.1, there exist many different ways to ChuckK. The choice of tools (WebChuckK, command

line ChuckK, miniAudicle, Chunity, etc.) depends on the task at hand. In other words, WebChuckK is not intended to be a replacement for any existing tool, but rather an expansion to the collective toolbox.

5.2 Future Work

Momentum favors the development of WebChuckK at this time, with ongoing efforts to ensure full-feature parity with the ChuckK on the desktop (e.g., including network communication like OSC, multichannel audio support, and variable sample rate) and with miniAudicle and its varied IDE features. Also, more tutorials are being created help users incorporate ChuckK into their web projects.²⁵

A fully usable WebChuckK IDE, similar to *p5.js*’s online editor, has already been developed by Terry Feng, Celeste Betancur, Mike Mulshine, and others. More work will be done to improve the IDE, including implementing a caching file system to organize full projects and enable users to return to all of their previous work between browser sessions. An audiovisual IDE combining WebChuckK and *p5.js* is also in the works, opening the door for students and artists to freely and easily prototype highly synchronized audiovisual systems.

Modeled after Google Docs, Overleaf, or Jupyter Notebook, the authors would like to develop a collaborative online WebChuckK editor (codenamed **WebChuckK Notebook**), to enable users to work on the same ChuckK project together simultaneously and remotely, embedding runnable ChuckK code inline with text and figures. This could be especially useful for educators teaching audio programming, ChuckK development teams, or artistic collaborators.

WebChuckK will continue to be co-developed via its various uses in computer music courses and artistic applications. As more people adopt the web as an accessible creative-computing medium, one might ponder:

*How much Web could a WebChuckK ChuckK, if we **all** could ChuckK on the Web?*

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors want to acknowledge and thank CCRMA (at Stanford University) for supporting its students and researchers who have contributed to the development of ChuckK and WebChuckK over the years. Special appreciate goes to the slew of web audio programmers, including especially Hongchan Choi, for developing the AudioWorklet interface, thus enabling ChuckK and other computer music programming languages (Csound, FAUST, Glicol) to run on the web.

7. ETHICAL STANDARDS

WebChuckK and ChuckK has been developed with the support of CCRMA’s departmental funding, curricular student research, and volunteer contributions. The authors are aware of no potential conflicts of interest. The students using early-stage WebChuckK were doing so to learn audio programming in a curricular context and were never treated as test subjects.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] Faust, a functional programming language for sound synthesis and audio processing.

<https://faust.grame.fr/>.

- ²⁵<https://chuck.stanford.edu/webchuck/tutorial/>

²³<https://fenglyfe.com/>

²⁴<https://www.celestebetancur.com/>

- [2] Faust, web-based functional sound synthesis programming ide. <https://faust.grame.fr/>.
- [3] *Estuary 0.3: Collaborative audio-visual live coding with a multilingual browser-based platform*. Zenodo, June 2022.
- [4] *Strudel: Algorithmic Patterns for the Web*. Zenodo, June 2022.
- [5] J. Atherton and G. Wang. Chunity: Integrated audiovisual programming in unity. In *New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, pages 102–107. Virginia Tech, June 2018.
- [6] H. Choi. Audio worklet: The future of web audio. In *International Conference on Music and Computing*, 2018.
- [7] Q. Lan and A. R. Jensenius. Glicol: A graph-oriented live coding language developed with rust, webassembly and audioworklet. In *Web Audio Conference*, 2021.
- [8] V. Lazzarini, E. Costello, S. Yi, and J. Fitch. Csound on the web. In *Linux Audio Conference*, 2014.
- [9] S. Letz, S. Denoux, and Y. Orlarey. Faust audio dsp language in the web. 2015.
- [10] Mozilla. Web Audio API. https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/API/Web_Audio_API.
- [11] T. Mudd. Gutter synthesis. <https://github.com/tommmudd/guttersynthesis>, 2018.
- [12] C. Roberts and M. Pachon-Puentes. Bringing the tidalcycles mini-notation to the browser. In *Web Audio Conference*, 2019.
- [13] S. Salazar, G. Wang, and P. R. Cook. miniaudicle and chuck shell: New interfaces for chuck development and performance. In *International Computer Music Conference*, 2006.
- [14] G. Wang. Ocarina: Designing the iPhone’s Magic Flute. *Computer Music Journal*, 38(2):8–21, 06 2014.
- [15] G. Wang. *Artful Design: Technology in Search of the Sublime*. Stanford University Press, 2018.
- [16] G. Wang and P. R. Cook. Chuck: A concurrent, on-the-fly audio programming language. In *International Computer Music Conference*, 2003.
- [17] G. Wang, P. R. Cook, and S. Salazar. Chuck: A strongly timed computer music language. *Computer Music Journal*, 39(4):10–29, 2015.
- [18] G. Wang and R. Michon. Fauck!! hybridizing the faust and chuck audio programming languages. In *Sound and Music Computing*, 2016.
- [19] S. Yi, H. Sigurðsson, and E. Costello. Csound web-ide. In *Web Audio Conference*, 2019.
- [20] M. Zbyszynski, M. Grierson, and M. J. Yee-King. Rapid prototyping of new instruments with codecircle. In *New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, 2017.